

Stakeholders' Readiness for Inclusive Education in Oyo and Osun State towards attaining Sustainable Development Goals in education system

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Abstract

The study examined stakeholders' readiness for inclusive education in Oyo and Osun States towards the attainment of sustainable development education system. It adopts a descriptive statistics and uses self-structured questionnaire to elicit information from a selected sample size of 400 respondents using a multi-stage sampling techniques. Information obtained were subjected to analysis using descriptive and inferential statistics using regression analysis and ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that although, inclusive education is well provided in Osun and Oyo State, but it gains prominence more in Osun State. The findings also revealed that stakeholders' readiness such as service/product behavioural, system, and infrastructural were all significant variables that could be used to enhance the provision of inclusive education towards the attainment of sustainable development in Osun and Oyo States, Nigeria. It is therefore recommended that Ministry of Education, NGOs, Teacher training Institutions, and several others should provide a continuous and regular training and workshops, particularly for the teachers, school administrators, and also to several other supporting stakeholders to propel better readiness among the stakeholders on the provision of inclusive education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Stakeholders Readiness, Inclusive Education, Children with special needs, Sustainable Development, Nigeria education system

Introduction

Education has a powerful potential to enhance development, which could include individual, family and society development, and also a major instrument to reduce poverty towards the

improvement of wellbeing in any nation (World Bank, 2024). Furthermore, it also tends to deliver large and consistent returns, with regards to the provision of enhanced income, couple with the fact that it is a major factor and tool that is deployed to achieve national or society equity and inclusion (World Bank, 2024). According to National Human Right Commission (2023), everyone has the right to education in Nigeria, However, Oshimade (2021) noted that very many individuals in Nigeria could not have access to education in the nation. This has been due to several factors such as poverty, ignorance, wrong cultural beliefs, among others (Eskay, Eskay & Uma, 2012; Oshimade, 2021). In addition, many children with special needs are not also able to have access to this education in Nigeria due to poverty, ignorance, wrong cultural beliefs (Eskay et al., 2012; Oshimade, 2021).

In addition, in order to drive education to meet the neglected, Sustainable development goal introduced SDG goals for inclusive education so as to make education reach to the neglected, this include the individuals with special needs. Inclusive education for persons with special needs could be defined as providing education of children with disabilities within the general education system (Catholic Relief Services (CRS) (2007).. According to the Federal Ministry of Education (2015), providing access to appropriate education for the Persons with Special Needs is a major thrust of inclusive education, and also it is a major goal of and tool for ensuring sustainable development in the nation because ot tilts towards the achievement of equity in inclusive education programmes. Although, Nigeria is very much involved in the provision of education for persons with Special Needs but it has several impediments such as bad classrooms, the lack of laboratories, no technology provided, the inability to address the cognitive domain of persons with special needs, among others (Federal Ministry of Education, 2015). All these connote the concept of stakeholders' readiness in the provision of inclusive education in Nigeria.

The concept of stakeholders' readiness captures the readiness of teachers, governments, policy makers, and the larger society public which include the parents, colleagues, and others with respect to the effective provision of inclusive education for the persons with special needs. (Indeed team, 2024). Adapting the S.W.I.T.C.H. Diamond Stakeholder Readiness model by Aheadahead (2011), there are some important elements that need to be put in consideration in examining stakeholders readiness. These elements are systematic, worldwide, integrated, transparent, collaborative, holistic and putting into considerations several other factors of measuring readiness such as service, product, behavioural, system, and infrastructural readiness.

The service and product readiness could include the readiness in the provision of inclusive education for the persons with special needs. The behavioural readiness explains the readiness of the stakeholders in the provision of inclusive education for the persons with special needs. The system readiness include the effectiveness of how the stakeholders are ready to be organized to work together towards ensuring success in the provision of inclusive education to the persons with special needs. Lastly, the infrastructural readiness includes the provision of various infrastructures and technologies that could foster the provision of inclusive education for the persons with special needs.

Putting into consideration that there could be access, quality and outcome gaps hence, the effects of these gaps could affect the over 10 million persons that are out-of-school children, and are denied access to education, which also include the persons with special needs, which in the long run could hinder development and thus create a drawback to the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria. In Southwestern Nigeria, which includes Oyo and Osun State, inclusive education for children with disabilities tends to face significant challenges such as poor the government and stakeholders' readiness thus, hindering the nation's propensity to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), particularly goal 4, which is the provision for inclusive and equitable quality education for all (Oluremi, 2015; Lawal, Onojah & Baniyaminu, 2025). Thus, there is need to address these major challenges towards the provision of Inclusive education for children with special needs. Therefore, this study focuses on examining stakeholders' readiness to Inclusive education for children with special needs in Oyo and Osun States, towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria education system. To this end, the following objectives are used to drive this study.

- i. Ascertaining the extent of the provision of inclusive education for children with special needs in Oyo and Osun States,
- ii. Examining stakeholders' readiness with respect to service/product, behavioural, system and infrastructural readiness, towards ensuring the provision of inclusive education for children with special needs in Oyo and Osun States.
- iii. Investigate the major challenges facing the provision of inclusive education for children with special needs in Oyo and Osun States.

Methodology

This descriptive survey design was used in this study, and drawing inference from the works of Creswell (2012); and Khatri (2020), a self-structured quantitative was used as the instrument to elicit necessary data and information from the respondents. The population of

this study consists of stakeholders of the education system in Oyo and Osun State, Nigeria. The study used a multiple sampling procedure to select participants and collect data. Also, the formula of Rose, Spinks and Canhoto (2015) for an unknown population was deployed to obtain the sample size for the respondents used in this study and it is given as:

$$n = 4pq/d^2$$

Where n= The sample size to be selected from an unknown population.

$$p= 0.5 \quad q= 1- p \text{ (which is also } 0.5)$$

d= 0.05 which is the error margin set for the study.

This error margin covers the probability of error in the study and in the selection showing that to an extent, the study is 95% error free and have error probability of 5%. Also, a total of 400 respondents is achieved from the use of the Rose et al.'s (2015) formula hence, 400 sample size was drawn to select the participants of the study. The study used a 4-likert scale instrument to elicit information from the respondents, and ten research assistants were used to cover Oyo and Osun States, supported by researcher. Data analysis involved the use of SPSS version 22 and the descriptive (frequency count and percentage) and inferential statistical (regression analysis and ANOVA) analysis method was used to analyse the data obtained from the field.

Results

The results of this study were presented with focus on the objectives of the study. The demographic characteristics of the respondents used were first provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographics Characteristics of Respondents

		State		Total
		OSUN	OYO	
Gender	Female	42(36.2%)	47(39.8%)	89(38.0%)
	Male	74(63.8%)	71(60.2%)	145(62.0%)
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)
Role as Stakeholder	Teachers	41(35.3%)	42(35.6%)	83(35.5%)
	Administrator	24(20.7%)	24(20.3%)	48(20.5%)
	Policy maker	3(2.6%)	9(7.6%)	12(5.1%)
	Parents	35(30.2%)	31(26.3%)	66(28.2%)
	Others	13(11.2%)	12(10.2%)	25(10.7%)
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)
Education level	OND/Diploma	20(17.2%)	8(6.8%)	28(12.0%)
	First degree	72(62.1%)	78(66.1%)	150(64.1%)
	Postgraduate	18(15.5%)	24(20.3%)	42(17.9%)
	Others	6(5.2%)	8(6.8%)	14(6.0%)
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)

The results in Table 1 above shows a cross tabulation of the demographic characteristics of the respondents with respect to the two States. The findings revealed that many of the respondents were from Oyo State having a higher percentage of 50.4% while respondents from Osun state represent 49.6%. Also, there were more males (62.0%) than females (38.0%) in the study, majority were teachers (35.5%), while very few were policy makers (5.1%). Also, respondents who possessed first degree had the highest percentage (64.1%), followed by those who had postgraduates (17.9%), while those with other qualifications attainment had 6.0%.

The extent to which inclusive education is provided is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Extent of Provision of Inclusive Education

		State		Total	Chi-Square Value
		OSUN	OYO		
Type of School in your area	Special School	30(25.9%)	19(16.1%)	49(20.9%)	3.366 ^a (p=.047)
	General school	86(74.1%)	99(83.9%)	185(79.1%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Prevalence of teachers with inclusive education skills in schools	No	70(60.3%)	90(76.3%)	160(68.4%)	6.862 ^a (p=.006)
	Yes	46(39.7%)	28(23.7%)	74(31.6%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Curriculum that addresses learners with different needs	No	38(32.8%)	61(51.7%)	99(42.3%)	8.594 ^a (p=.002)
	Yes	78(67.2%)	57(48.3%)	135(57.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Provision of adequate instructional materials	No	49(42.2%)	59(50.0%)	108(46.2%)	1.434 ^a (p=.488)
	Yes	67(57.7%)	59(50.0%)	126(53.8%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
School physical structures that are disability-friendly	No	77(66.4%)	87(73.7%)	164(70.1%)	1.507 ^a (p=.139)
	Yes	39(33.6%)	31(26.3%)	70(29.9%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Outdoor play areas that are disability-friendly	No	85(73.3%)	103(87.3%)	188(80.3%)	7.272 ^a (p=.005)
	Yes	31(26.7%)	15(12.7%)	46(19.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234*100.0%)	
Classrooms with enlarged entrances, ramps, uncracked floors, etc.	No	85(73.3%)	107(90.7%)	192(82.1%)	12.028 ^a (p=.000)
	Yes	31(26.7%)	11(9.3%)	42(17.9%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Disability-friendly sanitary facilities	No	104(89.7%)	116(98.3%)	220(94.0%)	7.781 ^a (p=.005)
	Yes	12(10.3%)	2(1.7%)	14(6.0%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Provision of counselors for meet divers of	No	111(95.7%)	113(95.8%)	224(95.7%)	.001 ^a (p=.615)
	Yes	5(4.3%)	5(4.2%)	10(4.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

students needs					
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There were significant differences across the provision of inclusive education between Oyo and Osun States. For example, with respect to whether the schools in their areas is special school or general school, with inclusive schools, there were more inclusive education in Osun State than in Oyo State ($p < .05$) implying that inclusive education is more in Osun State than in Oyo State. There was a significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with respect to the prevalence of teachers with inclusive education skills in schools with Osun State (39.7%) having more teachers with inclusive education skills than in Oyo State (23.7%) ($p < .05$). Also, there was a significant difference in the provision of curriculum that addresses learners with different needs between Oyo and Osun States ($p < .05$), higher in Osun State (67.2%) than in Oyo State (48.3%). This implies that Osun State has a higher extent of provision of inclusive education for persons with disabilities than Oyo State, Nigeria.

Also, the response of stakeholders' readiness towards inclusive education is provided in Table 3 to 6, with regards to the various constituents of stakeholders' readiness.

Table 3: Service Readiness

		State		Total	Chi-Square
		OSUN	OYO		
How aware are you of inclusive education	Not Aware	38(32.8%)	44(37.3%)	82(35.0%)	8.412 ^a (p=.038)
	Moderately	5(4.3%)	16(13.6%)	21(9.0%)	
	Aware	15(12.9%)	15(12.7%)	30(12.8%)	
	Very Aware	58(50.0%)	43(36.4%)	101(43.2%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How adequate are the availability of resources for inclusive education	Inadequate	34(29.3%)	41(34.7%)	75(32.1%)	2.651 ^a (p=.449)
	Moderately	8(6.9%)	13(11.0%)	21(9.0%)	
	Adequate	25(21.6%)	20(16.9%)	45(19.2%)	
	Very Adequate	49(42.2%)	44(37.3%)	93(39.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How Familiar are you with the provision of education services for students with diverse needs with the general students	Not Familiar	38(32.8%)	38(32.2%)	76(32.5%)	7.994 ^a (p=.046)
	Moderately	7(6.0%)	11(9.3%)	18(7.7%)	
	. Familiar	15(12.9%)	29(24.6%)	44(18.8%)	
	Very Familiar	56(48.3%)	40(33.9%)	96(41.0%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How adaptable is the Curriculum to meet students diverse learning needs	Not Adaptable	31(26.7%)	37(31.4%)	68(29.1%)	3.589 ^a (p=.309)
	Moderately	12(10.3%)	20(16.9%)	32(13.7%)	
	Adaptable	17(14.7%)	14(11.9%)	31(13.2%)	
	Highly	56(48.3%)	47(39.8%)	103(44.0%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

From Table 3, there were significant differences between Oyo and Osun States with regards to service readiness. For example, with respect to the extent of awareness of inclusive education ($p < .05$), it was higher in Osun States (67.2%) than in Oyo State (62.7%). There was a significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to the extent of how familiar are the stakeholders with respect to the provision of education services for students with diverse needs with the general students ($p < .05$), lower in Osun States (67.2%) than Oyo State (67.8%). How adaptable is the Curriculum to meet students diverse learning needs ($p > .05$). This implies that service readiness for the provision of inclusive education among the stakeholders is higher in Osun State than in Oyo State.

Table 4: Behavioural Readiness

		State		Total	Chi-Square
		OSUN	OYO		
How Comfortable do you think teachers are in teaching students with diverse abilities, including those with disabilities	Uncomfortable	42(36.2%)	42(35.6%)	84(35.9%)	3.152 ^a (p=.369)
	Moderately	14(12.1%)	8(6.8%)	22(9.4%)	
	Comfortable	16(13.8%)	13(11.0%)	29(12.4%)	
	Very Comfortable	44(37.9%)	55(46.6%)	99(42.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How extensive are training received on inclusive education practices for teachers	None	45(38.8%)	35(29.7%)	80(34.2%)	4.327 ^a (p=.228)
	Poor	12(10.3%)	12(10.2%)	24(10.3%)	
	Moderately	17(14.7%)	13(11.0%)	30(12.8%)	
	very extensive	42(36.2%)	58(49.2%)	100(42.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How Willing is the education stakeholders are to adapt divers teaching methods	Unwilling	43(37.1%)	39(33.1%)	82(35.0%)	4.724 ^a (p=.193)
	Moderately	14(12.1%)	9(7.6%)	23(9.8%)	
	Willing	21(18.1%)	16(13.6%)	37(15.8%)	
	Very Willing	38(32.8%)	54(45.8%)	92(39.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How do you Perceive inclusive education is beneficial	Not Beneficial	43(37.1%)	46(39.0%)	89(38.0%)	1.145 ^a (p=.766)
	Moderately	9(7.8%)	13(11.0%)	22(9.4%)	
	Beneficial	17(14.7%)	14(11.9%)	31(13.2%)	
	Very Beneficial	47(40.5%)	45(38.1%)	92(39.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

The results in Table 4 shows that, there was no significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to how comfortable teachers are in teaching students with diverse abilities, including those with disabilities ($p > 0.05$), how extensive are training received on inclusive education practices for teachers $p > 0.05$), among others. However, the percentage level of behavioral readiness seems to vary and has a stochastic path between Osun and Oyo

States. This implies that stakeholders possess certain behavioural readiness but has not translated to pose significant influence on effective inclusive education in both Osun and Oyo State.

Table 5: System Readiness

		State		Total	
		OSUN	OYO		
To what extent is school policies Supportiveness to achieve inclusive education	Not Supportive	35(30.2%)	51(43.2%)	86(36.8%)	5.350 ^a (p=.148)
	Moderately	10(8.6%)	11(9.3%)	21(9.0%)	
	somehow supportive	18(15.5%)	11(9.3%)	29(12.4%)	
	Very Supportive	53(45.7%)	45(38.1%)	98(41.9%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
To what extent are Systems put in place for identifying and supporting diverse needs	Not in Place	41(35.3%)	44(37.3%)	85(36.3%)	4.476 ^a (p=.214)
	Moderately	10(8.6%)	13(11.0%)	23(9.8%)	
	Established	23(19.8%)	12(10.2%)	35(15.0%)	
	Well Established	42(36.2%)	49(41.5%)	91(38.9%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
To what extent is there Collaboration among teachers, staff, and parents	Poor	48(41.4%)	40(33.9%)	88(37.6%)	1.735 ^a (p=.629)
	Moderately	12(10.3%)	13(11.0%)	25(10.7%)	
	Good	13(11.2%)	18(15.3%)	31(13.2%)	
	Excellent	43(37.1%)	47(39.8%)	90(38.5%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
To what extent is there Mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating inclusive practices	None	46(39.7%)	40(33.9%)	86(36.8%)	1.090 ^a (p=.779)
	Moderately	11(9.5%)	10(8.5%)	21(9.0%)	
	Robust	15(12.9%)	17(14.4%)	32(13.7%)	
	Very Robust	44(37.9%)	51(43.2%)	95(40.6%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

The results in Table 5 shows that, there was no significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to what extent do school policies support the achievement of inclusive education ($p > 0.05$), the extent to which systems are put in place for identifying and supporting diverse needs of students ($p > 0.05$), the extent to which there is collaboration among teachers, staff, and parents ($p > 0.05$), and the extent to which there is provision of mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating inclusive practices ($p > 0.05$). However, the percentage level of system readiness seems to vary and has a stochastic path between Osun and Oyo States. This implies there are provisions of certain systems for effective inclusive education but these have not pose positive significant impetus on effective inclusive education in both Osun and Oyo State.

Table 6: Infrastructural Readiness

		State		Total	
		OSUN	OYO		
How accessible are physical facilities towards enhancing inclusive education	Inaccessible	32(27.6%)	60(50.8%)	92(39.3%)	15.798 ^a (p=.001)
	Moderately	12(10.3%)	9(7.6%)	21(9.0%)	
	Accessible	13(11.2%)	15(12.7%)	28(12.0%)	
	Fully Accessible	59(50.9%)	34(28.8%)	93(39.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How available are resources for diverse needs	Inadequate	30(25.9%)	50(42.4%)	80(34.2%)	11.304 ^a (p=.010)
	Moderately	12(10.3%)	13(11.0%)	25(10.7%)	
	Adequate	28(24.1%)	30(25.4%)	58(24.8%)	
	very adequate	46(39.7%)	25(21.2%)	71(30.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
How Available are support staff	Inadequate	29(25.0%)	43(36.4%)	72(30.8%)	5.240 ^a (p=.155)
	Moderately	12(10.3%)	16(13.6%)	28(12.0%)	
	Adequate	32(27.6%)	24(20.3%)	56(23.9%)	
	very adequate	43(37.1%)	35(29.7%)	78(33.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
To what extent are Plans for infrastructure upgrades made	No Plans	29(25.0%)	46(39.0%)	75(32.1%)	5.991 ^a (p=.112)
	Moderately	16(13.8%)	13(11.0%)	29(12.4%)	
	Adequate	18(15.5%)	19(16.1%)	37(15.8%)	
	Comprehensive Plans	53(45.7%)	40(33.9%)	93(39.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

The results in Table 6 shows that, there is a significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to how accessible are physical facilities towards enhancing inclusive education ($p < 0.05$), higher in Osun States (72.4%) than Oyo State (49.1%). Also, there is a significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to how available are resources for diverse needs ($p < 0.05$), higher in Osun States (74.1%) than Oyo State (57.6%). However, there was no significant difference between Oyo and Osun States with regards to how Available are support staff ($p > 0.05$) and also to what extent are plans made for infrastructure upgrade ($p > 0.05$). This implies that infrastructural readiness is also higher in Osun State than in Oyo State for effective inclusive education.

The results also presented the various challenges facing the provision of inclusive education in Table 7.

Table 7: Challenges facing the Provision of Inclusive Education

		State		Total	Chi-Square
		OSUN	OYO		
Lack of resources	No	58(50.0%)	69(58.5%)	127(54.3%)	1.693 ^a (p=.193)
	Yes	58(50.0%)	49(41.5%)	107(45.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Insufficient training	No	68(58.6%)	73(61.9%)	141(60.3%)	.257 ^a (p=.612)
	Yes	48(41.4%)	45(38.1%)	93(39.7%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Limited accessibility	No	84(72.4%)	93(78.8%)	177(75.6%)	1.300 ^a (p=.254)
	Yes	32(27.6%)	25(21.2%)	57(24.4%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Technological difficulties	No	69(62.2%)	96(84.2%)	165(73.3%)	13.981 ^a (p=.000)
	Yes	42(37.8%)	18(15.8%)	60(26.7%)	
	Total	111(100.0%)	114(100.0%)	225(100.0%)	
Cultural barriers	No	105(90.5%)	96(81.4%)	201(85.9%)	4.053 ^a (p=.044)
	Yes	11(9.5%)	22(18.6%)	33(14.1%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Pedagogical issues	No	95(81.9%)	92(78.0%)	187(79.9%)	.563 ^a (p=.453)
	Yes	21(18.1%)	26(22.0%)	47(20.1%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Lack of awareness about data-driven learning	No	79(68.1%)	108(91.5%)	187(79.9%)	19.992 ^a (p=.000)
	Yes	37(31.9%)	10(8.5%)	47(20.1%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	
Poor ICT	No	111(95.7%)	113(95.8%)	224(95.7%)	.001 ^a (p=.978)
	Yes	5(4.3%)	5(4.2%)	10(4.3%)	
	Total	116(100.0%)	118(100.0%)	234(100.0%)	

The challenges facing the provision of inclusive education were provided in Table 7, and revealed that several challenges face the provision of inclusive education in Osun and Oyo State. These include the lack of resources, insufficient training, limited accessibility, technological difficulties, cultural barriers, pedagogical issues, lack of awareness about data-driven learning, and poor ICT. The findings of the study reveals that the lack of resources has the highest percentage of 45.7%, and higher in Osun State (50.0%) than in Oyo State (41.5%); followed by insufficient training provided for teachers possessing a percentage of 39.7%, and higher in Osun State (41.4%) than in Oyo State (38.1%).

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that most of the schools are general schools but inclusive educations are more in Osun State than in Oyo State. There were more teachers with inclusive education skills, provision of curriculum that addresses learners with different needs, school physical structures that are disability-friendly, provision of disability-friendly sanitary facilities, among others. To some extent, this has forfeited the notion of the National

Human Right Commission (2023) that everyone has the right to education in Nigeria. This juxtaposed the findings of Oshimade (2021) that in Nigeria, very many individuals do not have access to education. This bolsters the findings of Federal Ministry of Education (2015) that through, Nigeria is much involved in the provision of inclusive education but several impediments are still experienced in the process hence, making it impossible to completely achieve inclusive education in its education system. Drawing inference from the work of World Bank (2024), that education is a powerful potential for development and also very germane to reducing poverty and improves the wellbeing of individuals in the nation, individuals with special needs inclusive.

Several challenges facing the provision of inclusive education include the lack of resources, insufficient training, limited accessibility, technological difficulties, cultural barriers, pedagogical issues, lack of awareness about data-driven learning, and poor ICT. This concurs with the findings of Eskay et al. (2012) and Oshimade (2021) that inclusive education in Nigeria faces several challenges such as lack of knowledge and awareness, cultural beliefs, and so on. .

Also, stakeholders possess certain level of behavioural readiness in both Osun and Oyo State. There are also greater extents of infrastructural readiness, higher in Osun State than in Oyo State for effective inclusive education. The findings revealed that all the stakeholders' variables which are service readiness, behavioural readiness, system readiness, and infrastructural readiness, all pose joint significant effects on the extent of the provision of inclusive education. This implies that stakeholders' readiness which are service/product, behavioural, system, and infrastructural readiness, all pose significant impetus on the extent of the provision of inclusive education in both Osun and Oyo States. This corroborates with the S.W.I.T.C.H. Diamond Stakeholder Readiness model by [Aheadahead](#) (2011) that there is a dire need to put in place the service, behavioural, system and infrastructural readiness towards being able to achieve inclusive education that ensure sustainable development Thus, stakeholders readiness which cuts across the understanding of service/product, behavioural, system, and infrastructural readiness are very essential elements to enhance the provision of inclusive education that could inform the propensity to the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study examined stakeholders' readiness to inclusive education, particularly with focus on children with special needs in Oyo and Osun States, towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria education system. The findings revealed that although, inclusive education is well provided in Osun and Oyo State, but gain prominence more in Osun State, Nigeria. However, several challenges faced the provision of inclusive education such as the lack of resources, insufficient training, limited accessibility, cultural barriers, pedagogical issues, and others. The findings also revealed that stakeholders readiness such as service/product behavioural, system, and infrastructural were all significant variables that could be used to enhance the provision of inclusive education towards the attainment of sustainable development in Osun and Oyo States, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Several recommendations as provided below were provided from the findings of the study.

- i. Ministry of Education, NGOs, Teacher training Institutions, and several others should provide a continuous and regular training and workshops, particularly for the teachers, school administrators, and also to several other supporting stakeholders to propel better readiness among the stakeholders on the provision of inclusive education practices and necessary policies in Nigeria
- ii. Government, NGOs, Donor Agencies, and others should ensure the provision and allocation of adequate resources, which could include assistive technology, learning materials, and also support staff, towards the supporting of students with diverse needs to also propel the readiness among stakeholders to enhance inclusive education practices in Nigeria.
- iii. Ministry of Education and policymakers should develop and implement inclusive education policies that would promote education equity, access, and participation for all students in Nigeria, irrespective of any ailment or socio-economic setbacks.
- iv. Schools and teachers should engage with parents, community leaders, and communities, and local organizations to be able to raise serious awareness that could propel effective readiness among stakeholders towards the promotion of inclusive education practices in Nigeria schools and even in the society at large.

- v. Government, NGOs, Donor Agencies, and others should develop infrastructural by upgrading physical facilities to better ensure accessibility and inclusivity, particularly for students with disabilities.
- vi. Ministry of Education, Policymakers and others should provide administrative or leadership support for inclusive education initiatives.
- vii. Schools and teachers should ensure the participation of parents in decision-making processes and advocate for their children's needs, particularly those with special needs in Nigeria.
- viii. Government, Ministry of Education, Administrators, and others should establish a system for the monitoring and evaluating of inclusive education practices in Nigeria.

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